

LITERATURE LIST LINGUISTICS AND ETHNOGRAPHY OF WESTERN ARUNACHAL PRADESH

Note: This -incomplete- list only contains published sources and dissertations, although not all of them are readily available. A star * indicates particularly useful material from a language description perspective.

Hrusso AKA [hru]

Descriptive linguistics:

Anderson, James Drummond. 1896. *A Short Vocabulary of the Aka Language*. Shillong: Assam Secretariat Printing Office.

Shafer, Robert. 1947. Hruso. *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 12. 184-196.

Schubert, Johannes. 1964. Hrusso-Vokabular. *Mitteilungen des Instituts für Orientforschung* X. 295-350.

Simon, Ivan M. 1993 [1970]. *Aka language guide*. Itanagar: Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

D'Souza, Vijay A. 2015. *Towards a Phonology of Hrusso Aka*. University of Oxford MA thesis.

D'Souza, Vijay A. 2018. High vowel devoicing in Hrusso Aka. In Linda Konnerth and Stephen Morey and Amos Teo (eds.), *North East Indian Linguistics* 8, 33-46. Canberra: Asia-Pacific Linguistics.

*D'Souza, VA. 2021. *Aspects of Hrusso Aka phonology and morphology*. PhD dissertation. Oxford: University of Oxford, Linguistics Philology and Phonetics Faculty. <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:1f47a3ab-a444-4166-a4d7-3a26c6532610>

Other linguistics:

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Sinha, Nupur & Madhumita Barbora. 2021. Language Endangerment amongst Hruso-Aka and Koro. *SEL Journal* 6 (II). SEL. <https://selindia.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/vol-6-issue-2-2021-all.pdf>

Ethnographic and other:

Macgregor, Charles Reginal. 1885. Notes on Akas and Akaland. *Proceedings of the Asiatic Society of Bengal* 1884. 198-212.

Kennedy, R.S. 1914. *Ethnological Report on the Akas, Khowas, and Mijis and the Monbas of Tawang*. Shillong.

Sinha, Raghuvir. 1962. *The Akas*. Itanagar: Government of Arunachal Pradesh, Directorate of Research.

Grewal, Dalvinder Singh. 1993. *The Aka, Miji and their kindred in Arunachal Pradesh: An enquiry into the determinants of their identity*. University of North Bengal dissertation.

Dusu, Sambyo. 2013. *Akas of Arunachal Pradesh – A Historical Study till 1947 AD*. Doimukh: Rajiv Gandhi University dissertation.

SHERDUKPEN [sdp]

Descriptive linguistics:

North East Frontier Agency. 1954. *Dictionary of sentences "Sherdukpen"*. Shillong: Office of the Adviser to the Governor of Assam.

Dondrup, Rinchin. 1988. *A handbook on Sherdukpen language*. Itanagar: Shillong: The Philology Section, Research Department, North-East Frontier Agency.

*Jacquesson, François. 2015. *An Introduction to Sherdukpen Language*. Bochum: Brockmeyer.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2024. *Proto-Western Kho-Bwa: Reconstructing the past of a small indigenous community*. Language and Linguistics monograph series 67. Taipei: Institute of Linguistics, Academia Sinica.
https://www.ling.sinica.edu.tw/item/en?act=publish_book&code=view&bookID=146

Boro, Hirak. 2024. A preliminary study of Sherdukpen phonology. *Himalayan Linguistics*, 23-2: 35-52.

Other linguistics:

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Ethnolinguistic survey of westernmost Arunachal Pradesh: A fieldworker's impressions. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37.2: 198-239.

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Ethnographic and other:

- Sharma, R. R. P. 1988. *The Sherdukpens*. Itanagar: Government of Arunachal Pradesh.
- Dondrup, Megejee. 2011. *Stratification and change among the Sherdukpens An anthropological study on a Buddhist Tribe of Arunachal Pradesh*. Itanagar: Rajiv Gandhi University dissertation.
- Jacquesson, François and Pascale Dollfus. 2013. *Khiksaba, a Festival in Rupa Country*. Guwahati: Spectrum Publications.
- Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Notes on the settlement of the Gongri river valley of western Arunachal Pradesh. In Anna Balikci Denjongpa & Jenny Bentley (eds.) *The dragon and the hidden land: social and historical studies on Sikkim and Bhutan. Proceedings of the Bhutan-Sikkim panel at the 13th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, July 21-27, 2013. Bulletin of Tibetology* 50(1&2): 153–190.

BUGUN (KHOWA) [bgg]

Descriptive linguistics:

- Simon, I. M. 1976. The Khoa language. *Resarun: Journal of the Research Department, Government of Arunachal Pradesh* II(3). 8-10.
- Dondrup, Rinchin. 1990. *Bugun language guide*. Itanagar: Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh.
- Lander-Portnoy, Maury. 2013. *Let Buguns be Buguns: A Preliminary Phonetics, Phonology, and Morphology of the Bugun Language*. Swarthmore College MA thesis.
- Barbora, Madhumita. 2015. *Bugun nyo thau: Bugun reader*. Guwahati: EBH Publishers.
- Thakuria, Riniva. 2022. Word Formation in Bugun: Compounding and Affixation. *Language in India* Vol. 22:4.

Other linguistics:

- Barbora, Madhumita & Trisha Wangno. 2015. The Bugun language: Maintenance issues. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 38(2). 187-206.
- Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.
- Abraham, Binny & Kara Sako. 2021. Tagin and Puroik Tribes of Arunachal Pradesh: A Sociolinguistic Survey. *Journal of Language Survey Reports* 2021(063).

Ethnographic and other:

Kennedy, R.S. 1914. *Ethnological Report on the Akas, Khowas, and Mijis and the Monbas of Tawang*. Shillong.

Pandey, B. B. 1991. The Buguns or Khowas: An ethnographic profile. *Resarun: journal of the Research Department*, Government of Arunachal Pradesh XVII(1-2). 84-87.

Pandey, B. B. 1996. *The Buguns: A tribe in transition*. Delhi: Himalayan Publishers.

DUHUMBI (CHUGPA) [cvg]

Descriptive linguistics:

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2019. The Duhumbi perspective on Proto-Western Kho-Bwa rhymes. *Die Sprache* 52 (2016 / 2017) 2: 141–176.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2020. Expressives in Duhumbi. In: Nathan Badenoch & Nishaant Choksi (eds.) *Expressives of the South Asian linguistic area*, 278–299. Leiden: Brill.

*Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2020. *Grammar of Duhumbi (Chugpa)*. Leiden: Brill.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2020. *Duhumbi Dictionary*. Arnhem: Monpasang Publications.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2021. The Duhumbi perspective on Proto-Western Kho-Bwa onsets. *Journal of Historical Linguistics* 11(1): 1–59.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2024. *Proto-Western Kho-Bwa: Reconstructing the past of a small indigenous community*. Language and Linguistics monograph series 67. Taipei: Institute of Linguistics, Academia Sinica. https://www.ling.sinica.edu.tw/item/en?act=publish_book&code=view&bookID=146

Other linguistics:

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2018. *Duhumbi Storybook*. Arnhem: Monpasang Publications.

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Ethnographic and other:

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Ethnolinguistic survey of westernmost Arunachal Pradesh: A fieldworker's impressions. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37.2: 198-239.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Notes on the settlement of the Gongri river valley of western Arunachal Pradesh. In Anna Balikci Denjongpa & Jenny Bentley (eds.) *The dragon and the hidden land: social and historical studies on Sikkim and Bhutan. Proceedings of the Bhutan-Sikkim panel at the 13th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, July 21-27, 2013. Bulletin of Tibetology* 50(1&2): 153–190.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2024. Lessons from the Duhumbi version of the epic of King Gesar of Ling. *Proceedings of the 4th Vajrayāna conference*, October 1-4, 2022. Thimphu: Center for Bhutan and GNH Studies: 145–183.

TSHANGLA [tsj; kkf]

Descriptive linguistics:

Stack, Edward. 1897. *Some Tsangla-Bhutanese sentences: Part III*. Shillong: Assam Secretariat Printing Office.

Chaktavarty, L. N. 1953. *Dictionary of sentences Monpā (Dirang-Area)*. Shillong: North East Frontier Agency.

Hofrenning, Ralph W. 1959. *First Bhutanese grammar: Grammar of Gongar [=Tsangla], language of East Bhutan*. Madison.

Das Gupta, Kamalesh. 2007 [1968]. *An introduction to Central Monpa*. Shillong: Philology Section, Research Department, North East Frontier Agency.

Zhang, Jichuan. 1986. Cangluo Menbayu jianzhi [*A brief description of the Cangluo Menba language*]. Beijing: Nationalities Press. [in Chinese]

Hoshi, Michiyo. 1987. *A Sharchok vocabulary; A language spoken in Eastern Bhutan*. (Integral study on the ecology, languages and cultures of Tibet and Himalayas, 8.) Tokyo: Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa; Tokyo University of Foreign Studies.

Egli-Roduner, Susanna. 1987. *Handbook of the Sharchhokpa-lo/Tsangla (language of the people of Eastern Bhutan)*. Thimphu: Helvetas. Swiss Association for Development and Cooperation.

Wangdi, Pema. 2004. *Sharchhokpa-lo Phonology and Morphosyntax*. Australian National University MA thesis.

*Andvik, Erik E. 2010. *A Grammar of Tshangla*. Leiden: Brill.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Tshangla phonology and a standard Tshangla orthography. In: Thomas Owen-Smith & Nathan W. Hill (eds.) *Trans-Himalayan Linguistics*, 393–436. Berlin: deGruyter.

Dzongkha Development Commission. 2018. *Tshanglhai Drayang: A Tshangla-Dzongkha-English Lexicon*. Bhutan: Dzongkha Development Commission.

*Grollmann, Selin. 2020. *A Grammar of Bjokapakha*. Leiden: Brill.

Other linguistics:

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Ethnographic and other:

Bagchi, N. 1983. Socio-Cultural Profile of the Monpas of Kalaktang Areas. *Resarun XIII(1&2)*. 37-51.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2012. *The New Lamp Clarifying the History, Peoples, Languages and Traditions of Eastern Bhutan and Eastern Mon*. Wageningen: Monpasang Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1155036#>

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Ethnolinguistic survey of westernmost Arunachal Pradesh: A fieldworker's impressions. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37.2: 198-239.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Notes on the settlement of the Gongri river valley of western Arunachal Pradesh. In Anna Balikci Denjongpa & Jenny Bentley (eds.) *The dragon and the hidden land: social and historical studies on Sikkim and Bhutan*. Proceedings of the Bhutan-Sikkim panel at the 13th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, July 21-27, 2013. *Bulletin of Tibetology* 50(1&2): 153–190.

BROKPA [sgt]

Descriptive linguistics:

Dondrup, Rinchin. 1993. *Brokeh language guide*. Itanagar: Director of Research, Arunachal Pradesh Government.

Dzongkha Development Commission. 2016. *Dzongkha-Brokat Bi-lingual language book*. Bhutan: Dzongkha Development Commission. [in Dzongkha]

Gerber, Pascal, Selin Grollmann, Damian Funk, Sara Rüfenacht, Sereina Waldis, Corinne Mittaz & Tshering Leki. 2020. Aspects of Brokpa Grammar. *Himalayan Linguistics* 19(1). 1-262.

*Wangdi, Pema. 2021. *A Grammar of Brokpa: A Trans-Himalayan Language of Bhutan*. James Cook University dissertation.

Awan, Mechek Sampar. 2024. *Brokpa English Dictionary*. Itanagar: Centre for Endangered Languages, Arunachal Institute of Tribal Studies, Rajiv Gandhi University and Himalayan Publishers.

Ethnographic and other:

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2012. *The New Lamp Clarifying the History, Peoples, Languages and Traditions of Eastern Bhutan and Eastern Mon*. Wageningen: Monpasang Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1155036>

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Ethnolinguistic survey of westernmost Arunachal Pradesh: A fieldworker's impressions. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37.2: 198-239.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Notes on the settlement of the Gongri river valley of western Arunachal Pradesh. In Anna Balikci Denjongpa & Jenny Bentley (eds.) *The dragon and the hidden land: social and historical studies on Sikkim and Bhutan*. Proceedings of the Bhutan-Sikkim panel at the 13th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, July 21-27, 2013. *Bulletin of Tibetology* 50(1&2): 153-190.

Ramya, Tame. 2024. *Ethnographic profile of the Brokpa (Monpa) of Arunachal Pradesh*. Itanagar: Centre for Endangered Languages, Arunachal Institute of Tribal Studies, Rajiv Gandhi University and Himalayan Publishers.

Koro [jkr]

Descriptive linguistics:

Anderson, Gregory D. S.; and Murmu, Ganesh. 2010. Preliminary notes on Koro, a 'hidden' language of Arunachal Pradesh. *Indian Linguistics* 71: 1-32.

Geissler, Christopher. 2013. *Towards a Phonetic Description of Koro*. Swarthmore College MA thesis.

*Sinha, Nupur. 2021. *A descriptive grammar of Koro*. PhD dissertation. Tezpur: Tezpur University. http://agnee.tezu.ernet.in:8999/cgi-bin/koha/opac-detail.pl?biblionumber=58190&shelfbrowse_itemnumber=217761

Other linguistics:

Sinha, Nupur & Madhumita Barbora. 2021. Language Endangerment amongst Hruso-Aka and Koro. *SEL Journal* 6 (II). SEL. <https://selindia.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/vol-6-issue-2-2021-all.pdf>

Puroik (Sulung) [suv]

Descriptive linguistics:

Tayeng, Aduk. 1990. *Sulung language guide*. Itanagar: Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

Lǐ, Dàqín. 2004. *Sūlóngyǔ yánjiū [Research on Puroik]*. Běijīng: Mínzú chūbǎn shè (National Minorities Publisher). [in Chinese]

Remsangpuia. 2008. *Puroik phonology*. Shillong: Don Bosco Center for Indigenous Cultures.

Soja, Rai. 2009. *English-Puroik dictionary*. Shillong: Living Word Communicators.

*Lieberherr, Ismael. 2017. *A grammar of Bulu Puroik*. PhD thesis, Universität Bern.

Other linguistics:

Lieberherr, Ismael. 2015. A progress report on the historical phonology and affiliation of Puroik. In: Linda Konnerth et al. (eds.), *North East Indian linguistics* Vol. 7, 235–286. Canberra: AsiaPacific Linguistics, Australian National University.

Abraham, Binny & Kara Sako. 2021. *Tagin and Puroik Tribes of Arunachal Pradesh: A Sociolinguistic Survey*. *Journal of Language Survey Reports* 2021(063). 1-83.

Ethnographic and other:

Stonor, Charles Robert. 1952. The Sulung tribe of the Assam Himalayas. *Anthropos* 47: 947–962.

Deuri, R. K. 1983. *The Sulungs*. Shillong: Research Department, Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

Miji (Sajolang) [sjl]

Descriptive linguistics:

Simon, I. M. 1979. *Miji Language Guide*. Shillong: Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

*Weedall, Christopher. 2021. *A grammar of West Kameng Sajolang (Miji): (Upper Dzang and Khellong villages)*. PhD dissertation. Canberra: Australian National University. DOI: 10.25911/N56D-MS43

Other linguistics:

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Ethnographic and other:

Kennedy, R.S. 1914. *Ethnological Report on the Akas, Khowas, and Mijis and the Monbas of Tawang*. Shillong.

Bangru

Descriptive linguistics:

Lǐ, Dàqín. 2003. Bēngrú-yǔ gàikuàng [Bangru language overview]. *Minzu Yuwen*, (5):64-80. [in Chinese]

Other linguistics:

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus; and Lieberherr, Ismael. 2015. First notes on the phonology and classification of the Bangru language of India. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 38.1: 66-123.

Ethnographic and other:

Ramya, T. 2011. *An Ethnographic Study of Bangrus of Kurung Kumey District of Arunachal Pradesh*. MA. Tribal Studies. Doimukh: Rajiv Gandhi University.

Ramya, T. 2012. Bangrus of Arunachal Pradesh: An Ethnographic Profile. *International Journal of Social Science Tomorrow*, 1(3):1-12.

Tawang Monpa [dka; twm]

Descriptive linguistics:

Lu, Shaozun. 1986. Cuona Menbayu jianzhi [A brief description of the Cuona Menba language]. Beijing: Nationalities Press. [in Chinese]

Lu, Shaozun. 2002. Ménbā yǔ fāngyán yánjiū [Studies on the dialects of the Monpa language]. Beijing: Nationalities Press. [in Chinese]

Wangchu, Lhama. 2002. *An introduction to the Tawang Monpa language*. Itanagar: Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

*Tombleson, Anette Helgestad. 2022. *Grammar Sketch of Tawang Monpa*. *Himalayan Linguistics* 21(2). 105-141.

Other linguistics:

Nishida, Tatsuo. 1988. The Mtsho-Sna Monpa language of China and its place in the Tibeto-Burman family. In David Bradley and Eugénie J. A. Henderson and Martine Mazaudon (eds.), *Prosodic analysis and Asian linguistics: To honour R.K. Sprigg*, 223-236. Canberra: Australian National University.

Driem, George van. 2007. Dzala and Dakpa form a coherent subgroup within East Bodish, and some related thoughts. In Bielmeier, Roland and Haller, Felix (eds.), *Linguistics of the Himalayas and beyond*, 71-84. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.

Hyslop, Gwendolyn & Karma Tshering. 2008. Preliminary Notes on Dakpa (Tawang Monpa). In Stephen Morey and Mark Post (eds.), *North East Indian Linguistics Volume 2*, 1-22. New Delhi: Cambridge University Press India.

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2023. East Bodish revisited. *Bulletin of Tibetology* 54 (1): 49-212.

Ethnographic and other:

Kennedy, R.S. 1914. *Ethnological Report on the Akas, Khowas, and Mijis and the Monbas of Tawang*. Shillong.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2012. *The New Lamp Clarifying the History, Peoples, Languages and Traditions of Eastern Bhutan and Eastern Mon*. Wageningen: Monpasang Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1155036>

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Ethnolinguistic survey of westernmost Arunachal Pradesh: A fieldworker's impressions. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37.2: 198-239.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Notes on the settlement of the Gongri river valley of western Arunachal Pradesh. In Anna Balikci Denjongpa & Jenny Bentley (eds.) *The dragon and the hidden land: social and historical studies on Sikkim and Bhutan*. Proceedings of the Bhutan-Sikkim panel at the 13th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, July 21-27, 2013. *Bulletin of Tibetology* 50(1&2): 153-190.

Sartang (Boot Monpa) [onp]

Descriptive linguistics:

Dondrup, Rinchin. 2004. *An introduction to the Boot Monpa language*. Itanagar: Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2024. *Proto-Western Kho-Bwa: Reconstructing the past of a small indigenous community*. Language and Linguistics monograph series 67. Taipei: Institute of Linguistics, Academia Sinica. https://www.ling.sinica.edu.tw/item/en?act=publish_book&code=view&bookID=146

Other linguistics:

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2021. Sartang (West Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh, India) - Language Contexts. *Language Documentation and Description* 20. 162-188.

Ethnographic and other:

Dondrup, Rinchin. 1987. The migration of the Monpas of Boot area in West Kameng district. *Resarun: Journal of the Research Department, Government of Arunachal Pradesh XIII*. 28-30.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Ethnolinguistic survey of westernmost Arunachal Pradesh: A fieldworker's impressions. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37.2: 198-239.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Notes on the settlement of the Gongri river valley of western Arunachal Pradesh. In Anna Balikci Denjongpa & Jenny Bentley (eds.) *The dragon and the hidden land: social and historical studies on Sikkim and Bhutan*. Proceedings of the Bhutan-Sikkim panel at the 13th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, July 21-27, 2013. *Bulletin of Tibetology* 50(1&2): 153-190.

Khispi (Lishpa) [lsh]

Descriptive linguistics:

Bodt, Timotheus A. 2024. *Proto-Western Kho-Bwa: Reconstructing the past of a small indigenous community*. Language and Linguistics monograph series 67. Taipei: Institute of Linguistics, Academia Sinica.

https://www.ling.sinica.edu.tw/item/en?act=publish_book&code=view&bookID=146

Other linguistics:

Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International.

Ethnographic and other:

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Ethnolinguistic survey of westernmost Arunachal Pradesh: A fieldworker's impressions. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 37.2: 198-239.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus. 2014. Notes on the settlement of the Gongri river valley of western Arunachal Pradesh. In Anna Balikci Denjongpa & Jenny Bentley (eds.) *The dragon and the hidden land: social and historical studies on Sikkim and Bhutan. Proceedings of the Bhutan-Sikkim panel at the 13th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia, July 21-27, 2013. Bulletin of Tibetology* 50(1&2): 153-190.

Historical and comparative linguistics:

Michailovsky, Boyd & Martine Mazaudon. 1994. *Preliminary Notes on the Languages of the Bumthang group*. In Per Kvaerne (ed.), *Proceedings of the 6th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Fagernes 1992*, 545-557. The Institute for Comparative Research in Human Culture. [East Bodish]

Hyslop, Gwendolyn. 2014. A preliminary reconstruction of East Bodish. In Nathan Hill and Thomas Owen-Smith (eds.), *Trans-Himalayan Linguistics*, 155-179. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter. [East Bodish]

Blench, Roger; and Post, Mark W. 2014. Rethinking Sino-Tibetan phylogeny from the perspective of Northeast Indian languages. In: Thomas Owen-Smith and Nathan W. Hill (eds.), *Trans-Himalayan-Linguistics*, 71-104. Berlin: de Gruyter.

Bodt, Timotheus Adrianus; and Lieberherr, Ismael. 2015. First notes on the phonology and classification of the Bangru language of India. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 38.1: 66-123. [Hrusish]

Lieberherr, Ismael & Timotheus Adrianus Bodt. 2017. Sub-grouping Kho-Bwa based on shared core vocabulary. *Himalayan Linguistics* Vol. 16(1): 26-63. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4t27h5fg>

- Abraham, Binny, Kara Sako, Elina Kinny & Isapdaile Zeliang. 2018 [2005]. *Research among Selected Groups in Western Arunachal Pradesh: Highlighting Monpa*. (SIL Electronic Survey Reports, 2018-009.) Dallas, Texas: SIL International. [Kho-Bwa, Tshangla, Dakpa, Hrusish]
- Bodt, Timotheus A. & Johann-Mattis List. 2019. Testing the predictive force of the comparative method: An ongoing experiment on unattested words in Western Kho-Bwa languages. *Papers in Historical Phonology* Volume 4: 22–44. <http://journals.ed.ac.uk/pihph/issue/view/253> [Western Kho-Bwa]
- Abraham, Binny & Kara Sako. 2021. *Tagin and Puroik Tribes of Arunachal Pradesh: A Sociolinguistic Survey*. *Journal of Language Survey Reports* 2021(063). [Kho-Bwa]
- Wu, Mei-Shin, Timotheus A. Bodt & Tiago Tresoldi. 2022. Bayesian phylogenetics illuminate shallower relationships among Trans-Himalayan languages in the Tibet-Arunachal area. *Linguistics of the Tibeto-Burman Area* 45(2): 171–210. [Hrusish, East Bodish, Tshangla, Kho-Bwa]
- Bodt, Timotheus A. 2023. East Bodish revisited. *Bulletin of Tibetology* 54 (1): 49-212. [East Bodish]
- Tournadre, Nicolas & Hiroyuki Suzuki. 2023. *The Tibetic languages: An introduction to the family of languages derived from Old Tibetan*. Paris: LACITO. [Bodic]
- Blench, Roger. 2024. *(De)classifying Arunachal languages: Reconsidering the evidence*. *Mother Tongue* XXV. 63-93. [Kho-Bwa, Bodic, Hrusish]
- Bodt, Timotheus A. 2024. *Proto-Western Kho-Bwa: Reconstructing the past of a small indigenous community*. Language and Linguistics monograph series 67. Taipei: Institute of Linguistics, Academia Sinica. https://www.ling.sinica.edu.tw/item/en?act=publish_book&code=view&bookID=146 [Western Kho-Bwa]